

Lower and Upper Soft Interval Valued Neutrosophic Rough Approximations of An IVNSS-Relation

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Abstract: In this paper, we extend the lower and upper soft interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy rough approximations of IVIFS –relations proposed by Anjan et al. to the case of interval valued neutrosophic soft set relation(IVNSS-relation for short)

Keywords: Interval valued neutrosophic soft , Interval valued neutrosophic soft set relation

0. Introduction

This paper is an attempt to extend the concept of interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy soft relation (IVIFSS-relations) introduced by A. Mukherjee et al [45]to IVNSS relation .

The organization of this paper is as follow: In section 2, we briefly present some basic definitions and preliminary results are given which will be used in the rest of the paper. In section 3, relation interval neutrosophic soft relation is presented. In section 4 various type of interval valued neutrosophic soft relations. In section 5, we concludes the paper

1. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, let U be a universal set and E be the set of all possible parameters under consideration with respect to U , usually, parameters are attributes, characteristics, or properties of objects in U . We now recall some basic notions of neutrosophic set, interval neutrosophic set, soft set, neutrosophic soft set and interval neutrosophic soft set.

Definition 2.1.

Let U be an universe of discourse then the neutrosophic set A is an object having the form $A = \{ \langle x: \mu_{A(x)}, \nu_{A(x)}, \omega_{A(x)} \rangle, x \in U \}$, where the functions $\mu, \nu, \omega : U \rightarrow]0, 1^+[$ define respectively the degree of membership , the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition.

$$0 \leq \mu_{A(x)} + \nu_{A(x)} + \omega_{A(x)} \leq 3^+.$$

From philosophical point of view, the neutrosophic set takes the value from real standard or non-standard subsets of $]0,1+[$.so instead of $]0,1+[$ we need to take the interval $[0,1]$ for technical applications, because $]0,1+[$ will be difficult to apply in the real applications such as in scientific and engineering problems.

Definition 2.2. A neutrosophic set A is contained in another neutrosophic set B i.e. $A \subseteq B$ if $\forall x \in U, \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x), \omega_A(x) \geq \omega_B(x)$.

Definition 2.3. Let X be a space of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x. An interval valued neutrosophic set (for short IVNS) A in X is characterized by truth-membership function $\mu_A(\mathbf{x})$, indeterminacy-membership function $\nu_A(\mathbf{x})$ and falsity-membership function $\omega_A(\mathbf{x})$. For each point x in X, we have that $\mu_A(\mathbf{x}), \nu_A(\mathbf{x}), \omega_A(\mathbf{x}) \in [0, 1]$.

For two IVNS , $A_{IVNS} =\{ \langle x, [\mu_A^L(x), \mu_A^U(x)] , [\nu_A^L(x), \nu_A^U(x)] , [\omega_A^L(x), \omega_A^U(x)] \rangle \mid x \in X \}$ And $B_{IVNS} =\{ \langle x, [\mu_B^L(x), \mu_B^U(x)] , [\nu_B^L(x), \nu_B^U(x)] , [\omega_B^L(x), \omega_B^U(x)] \rangle \mid x \in X \}$ the two relations are defined as follows:

- (1) $A_{IVNS} \subseteq B_{IVNS}$ if and only if $\mu_A^L(x) \leq \mu_B^L(x), \mu_A^U(x) \leq \mu_B^U(x), \nu_A^L(x) \geq \nu_B^L(x), \nu_A^U(x) \geq \nu_B^U(x), \omega_A^L(x) \geq \omega_B^L(x), \omega_A^U(x) \geq \omega_B^U(x)$ for any $x \in X$
- (2) $A_{IVNS} = B_{IVNS}$ if and only if $\mu_A(x) = \mu_B(x), \nu_A(x) = \nu_B(x), \omega_A(x) = \omega_B(x)$ for any $x \in X$

As an illustration ,let us consider the following example.

Example 2.4. Assume that the universe of discourse $U = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$, where x_1 characterizes the capability, x_2 characterizes the trustworthiness and x_3 indicates the prices of the objects. It may be further assumed that the values of x_1, x_2 and x_3 are in $[0,1]$ and they are obtained from some questionnaires of some experts. The experts may impose their opinion in three components viz. the degree of goodness, the degree of indeterminacy and that of poorness to explain the characteristics of the objects. Suppose A is an interval neutrosophic set (INS) of U, such that,
 $A = \{ \langle x_1, [0.3 \ 0.4], [0.5 \ 0.6], [0.4 \ 0.5] \rangle, \langle x_2, [0.1 \ 0.2], [0.3 \ 0.4], [0.6 \ 0.7] \rangle, \langle x_3, [0.2 \ 0.4], [0.4 \ 0.5], [0.4 \ 0.6] \rangle \}$, where the degree of goodness of capability is 0.3, degree of indeterminacy of capability is 0.5 and degree of falsity of capability is 0.4 etc.

Definition 2.5.

Let U be an initial universe set and E be a set of parameters. Let P(U) denotes the power set of U. Consider a nonempty set A, $A \subset E$. A pair (K, A) is called a soft set over U, where K is a mapping given by $K : A \rightarrow P(U)$.

As an illustration, let us consider the following example.

Example 2.6 .

Suppose that U is the set of houses under consideration, say $U = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_5\}$. Let E be the set of some attributes of such houses, say $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_8\}$, where $e_1, e_2, \dots, e_8$ stand for the attributes "beautiful", "costly", "in the green surroundings", "moderate", respectively. In this case, to define a soft set means to point out expensive houses, beautiful houses, and so on. For example, the soft set (K,A) that describes the "attractiveness of the houses" in the opinion of a buyer, say Thomas, may be defined like this:

$$A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5\};$$

$$K(e_1) = \{h_2, h_3, h_5\}, K(e_2) = \{h_2, h_4\}, K(e_3) = \{h_1\}, K(e_4) = U, K(e_5) = \{h_3, h_5\}.$$

Definition 2.7 .

Let U be an initial universe set and A $\subset$ E be a set of parameters. Let IVNS(U) denotes the

Again as $\min(\inf v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}, \inf v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \leq \inf v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x)$, and
 $\min(\inf v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}, \inf v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \leq \inf v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)$

we have

$$\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\min(\inf v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x), \inf v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \vee \inf v_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)) \leq \text{Min} (\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\inf v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \inf v_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)), \bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\inf v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \inf v_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x))).$$

Similarly we can get

$$\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\min(\sup v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x), \sup v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \vee \sup v_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)) \leq \text{Min} (\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\sup v_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \sup v_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)), \bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\sup v_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \sup v_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x))).$$

Again as $\min(\inf \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}, \inf \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \leq \inf \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x)$, and
 $\min(\inf \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}, \inf \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \leq \inf \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)$

we have

$$\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\min(\inf \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x), \inf \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \vee \inf \omega_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)) \leq \text{Min} (\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\inf \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \inf \omega_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)), \bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\inf \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \inf \omega_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x))).$$

Similarly we can get

$$\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\min(\sup \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x), \sup \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x)) \vee \sup \omega_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)) \leq \text{Min} (\bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\sup \omega_{\mathbf{G}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \sup \omega_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x)), \bigwedge_{e_j \in A} (\sup \omega_{\mathbf{H}(e_i, e_j)}(x) \vee \sup \omega_{\mathbf{f}(e_k)}(x))).$$

Consequently $\text{Lwr}_S(\mathbf{R}_1) \cup \text{Lwr}_S(\mathbf{R}_2) \subseteq \text{Lwr}_S(\mathbf{R}_1 \cap \mathbf{R}_2)$

(vii) Proof is similar to (vii).

Conclusion

In the present paper we extend the concept of Lower and upper soft interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy rough approximations of an IVIFSS-relation to the case IVNSS and investigated some of their properties.

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